

MEANS OF LEXICAL-SEMANTIC EXPRESSION OF THE PHILOSOPHY OF HUMANISM AND SPIRITUAL-MORAL CONCEPTS IN THE DRAMAS OF U. SHAKESPEARE AND A. FITRAT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472737>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 13th December 2022

Accepted: 21th December 2022

Online: 22th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Pathos, tragedy, renaissance, genre, dramatic, criterion, classification, happy, unhappiness, scene.

ABSTRACT

Exalting the dignity of a person, considering him as the highest value, created a new spiritual environment for the further development of the ideal of freedom. The roots of Renaissance natural philosophy go back to the ancient Greek philosophical heritage, in particular to Platonism, Stoic pantheism, and Ionic philosophy.

"Arastu emphasizes that pathos is manifested through the tragedy of the hero, his mental anguish and arouses the corresponding feelings in the audience.

If Hegel interprets pathos in connection with "family, homeland, church, glory, friendship, pride, honor, love" characteristic of the characters of the work, according to V. Belinsky, it is an "idea-passion" related to the personality of the creator, and pathos is the author's spiritual-spiritual. The world comes from the senses of perception of the world. G. Pospelov interprets it as one of the important elements of artistic content. In "Dictionary of Literary Studies":

The scientist emphasizes his opinion that in the genre classification of a lyrical work, attention to the formal aspect leads to attention, while differences in content are not denied. He tries to prove his ideas on the example of the types of musammat based on the band structure and the genres of rubai and fard. Also, he explains the reason why some specialists classify

"Abulfayzkhan" as a drama, and some as a tragedy, and reminds that Aristotle founded the rule that pathos is the main criterion in the genre classification of dramatic works.

It is known that Aristotle, speaking about the internal division of tragedy, distinguishes three cases: "Passion is an act that causes destruction or suffering." Tragedy genre based on sharp turn, sudden knowledge, passion "a well-constructed narrative should be relatively simple, and the fate should change in it not from misfortune to happiness, but rather from misfortune to happiness, not as a result of sin, but on the contrary, because of a great mistake made by a good person rather than a bad one." based on the above, it can be said that the backbone of tragedy is tragic pathos, and if there is no pathos, none of the evils such as death and murder can be a tragedy.

When Shakespeare created "Hamlet", he was 37 years old, he deepened his thoughts as a creator, gained a certain experience,

was full of creative energy, his views on the complexities of life were firm, and the wonderful world of art appeared in his psyche with all its beauty. The tragedy was staged in 1601 and published in 1603. A year later, the first edition was seriously revised and expanded. Shakespeare scholar A. Anikst said that the philosophical essence of the tragedy was deepened in the second edition, the image of the main character Hamlet was changed, and his concept as a human being was shown in all its complexities. At that time, the author was 40 years old, and his creative maturity was at its peak. "When approaching forty years old, - writes I. Haqqul, - tragic pathos began to dominate in Shakespeare's work. As many people recognize, Hamlet is the pinnacle of Shakespeare's literary legacy. The literature of the world still does not know of a second work that could conquer this height." In fact, Hamlet is a guardian of the family, a devotee of society, a loyal and conscientious citizen of the state, honor and dignity, a leader of faith, the hope and future of a declining country, moreover, the heir to the throne bleeding from betrayal. He embodies all the good qualities characteristic of a real person, and that is why he is still loved and honored in the hearts of the peoples of the world, in different climatic regions.

The similarity between "Hamlet" and "Abulfayzkhan's tragedies" is manifested in the psychology of the characters, their suffering and inner feelings. In "Hamlet" Claudius secretly kills his brother -

Hamlet's father and takes over his throne and marries his brother's wife, in "Abulfaiz Khan" Abulfaiz Khan also kills his own brother and thus both of them take the throne. Claudius, even Abulfaiz Khan, who became the murderer of his seven children, creates his own tragedy.

Tragedy understood as an aesthetic category, first of all, the contradiction that inevitably arises in a certain dramatic situation, has a tragic essence in the full sense. A tragic situation is an irreconcilable conflict, a tragic situation that cannot be resolved positively. When we say the solution, the hero goes to his tragedy, his mistake, sin, ignorant, cowardly and vengeful to praise, the khan thus loses his strong, reliable and wise adviser.

In "Hamlet" tragedy, Hamlet's father is poisoned by mercury-like poison in his ear, Hamlet's mother is poisoned, and Hamlet commits suicide by poisoning himself with a sword.

In "Hamlet", the Ghost of the King, who reveals the secret, reveals. When the widow explains that she is doomed to burn in hell during the day, that this reproach, that the black trade will continue until she is cleansed of sin, but that she cannot reveal the secrets about it, she talks about how Hamlet's soul will die if he tells what happened to him, and his eyes will leave his room like stars shot from their axes, and he this urges him to take revenge on the murderer.

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